

Phospho sulfonic acid catalysed mild and efficient synthesis of 2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-ones in aqueous ethanol medium

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Abstract : An efficient synthesis of 2,3-dihydro-2-phenylquinazolin-4(1H)-ones have been developed via one-pot reaction from arylaldehydes and 2-aminobenzamide catalyzed by phospho sulfonic acid (PSA) in aqueous ethanol medium. The present methodology offers several advantages, such as simple procedure with an easy work-up, high yields and short reaction times. Moreover, the catalyst can be easily recovered and reused at least four times with only slight reduction in its catalytic activity.

Keywords : Phospho sulfonic acid (PSA), 2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-one, 2-amino benzamide, catalyst recovery.

Introduction

Dihydroquinazolinones have drawn tremendous attention in recent years because of their pharmacological, biological and medicinal activities such as antitumor¹, α_1 -adreno receptor antagonists², antimicrobial³, insecticidal activities against oriental armyworm⁴ and 5-HT₇ receptor⁵. 2,3-Dihydro-2-phenylquinazolin-4(1H)-ones are potent tubulin inhibitors with extraordinary anti-proliferative activity against several human cancers with very low IC₅₀ value. These dihydroquinazolinones act analogously to colchicine (inhibitors of tubulin polymerization) by binding to α , β -tubulin⁶. A series of new 3,5-diaryl isoxazoline/isoxazole linked 2,3-dihydro quinazolinone hybrids with different linker architectures have been designed and synthesized. These compounds have been evaluated for their anticancer activity⁷. In view of these useful properties, development of a simple, environmentally benign, high-yielding, and clean method for the synthesis of 2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-ones is still in demand.

Various approaches toward the synthesis of this class of compounds have been explored but the most convenient method for the synthesis of 2,3-dihydro-4(1H)-quinazolinones is the condensation of 2-anthranilamide with aldehydes or ketones. Various catalysts, such as gallium trifluoro methane sulfonate⁸, sulfamic acid⁹,

trifluoroethanol¹⁰, supramolecular synthesis¹¹, heteropoly acids¹², amberlyst-15¹³, pentafluorophenylammonium triflate-CuCl₂¹⁴ and aerosil silica supported acidic ionic liquid¹⁵ have been used to promote this reaction. Three-component reaction of isatoic anhydride, aldehyde and amine are also reported for the synthesis of 2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-ones¹⁶⁻¹⁹. However, most of these methods suffer from extended reaction times, low yields, use of costly reagents, vigorous reaction conditions and also requirement of tedious work-up procedures. Therefore, development of a simple, efficient, atom economic, inexpensive and environment friendly process for the synthesis of quinazolinones is highly desirable.

Green chemistry can be recognized as a pioneering research, which widely reports intrinsic atom economy, energy savings, waste reduction, easy work ups and the avoidance of hazardous chemicals. The most advantageous way of carrying out a chemical synthesis is by applying the principles of green chemistry such that the by products are either minimized or eliminated²⁰. Research towards the development and application of solid acids as economically and environmentally benign catalysts has attracted considerable attention from both academia and industry, because as well as being inexpensive and environmentally friendly, these reagents are non-corrosive and

their disposal does not lead to any significant effluent problems^{21,22}.

Recently, phospho sulfonic acid has been used as a catalyst for the synthesis of indazolo[1,2-*b*]phthalazinetriones²³, 14-aryl-14*H*-dibenzo[*a,j*]xanthenes²⁴ and bis-(4-hydroxycoumarin-3-yl)methanes²⁵. In continuation of our previous works on the development of new eco-friendly methods for the synthesis of biologically active organic compounds, such as 2-substituted benzothiozoles²⁶, 1,4-dihydropyridines²⁷, 2-amino-4,6-diphenylnicotinonitrile²⁸, 2,6-dimethyl-4-substituted-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-diethyl carboxylate derivatives²⁹ and pyrano[4,3-*b*]pyran derivatives³⁰ we now describe the synthesis of 2,3-dihydro-2-phenylquinazolin-4(*1H*)-ones using catalytic amount of phosphosulfonic acid (PSA) via the cyclocondensation of 2-aminobenzamide with an aldehyde in EtOH-H₂O (1 : 1) at 60 °C (Scheme 1).

Results and discussion

We report herein, a simple, mild, and expeditious synthesis of 2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(*1H*)-ones in excel-

Scheme 1. Preparation of various 2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(*1H*)-ones.

lent yields employing PSA (5 mol%) as an efficient catalyst in EtOH-H₂O (1 : 1) at 60 °C (Scheme 1).

In the initial experiment, we investigated various conditions in the model reaction of 2-aminobenzamide (1 mmol) with benzaldehyde (1 mmol) in the presence of PSA under thermal condition and the results were summarized in Table 1. The effect of various solvents such as EtOH, CH₃CN, 1,4-dioxane, DMF, THF and water on the model reaction was conducted in the presence of PSA (Table 1, entries 1–6). The reaction under solvent-free condition also carried out (Table 1, entry 7). The reactions in refluxing protic solvents such as water or EtOH gave better yields (Table 1, entries 1 and 6). Hence, the model reaction was studied at EtOH-H₂O (1 : 1) solvent

Table 1. Optimization of the reaction conditions on the synthesis of 2,3-dihydro-2-phenylquinazolin-4(*1H*)-ones **3a**^a

Entry	Catalyst	Amount	Solvent	Temp. (°C)	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^b
1	PSA	5 mol %	EtOH	Reflux	90	85
2	PSA	5 mol %	CH ₃ CN	Reflux	240	62
3	PSA	5 mol %	1,4-Dioxane	Reflux	240	45
4	PSA	5 mol %	DMF	Reflux	240	55
5	PSA	5 mol %	THF	Reflux	210	49
6	PSA	5 mol %	Water	Reflux	90	82
7	PSA	5 mol %	Solvent-free	70	180	66
8	PSA	5 mol %	EtOH-H ₂ O (1 : 1)	60	45	94
9	PSA	0 mol %	EtOH-H ₂ O (1 : 1)	60	180	24
10	PSA	2 mol %	EtOH-H ₂ O (1 : 1)	60	120	55
11	PSA	3 mol %	EtOH-H ₂ O (1 : 1)	60	80	70
12	PSA	7 mol %	EtOH-H ₂ O (1 : 1)	60	45	94
13	PSA	5 mol %	EtOH-H ₂ O (1 : 1)	rt	75	66
14	PSA	5 mol %	EtOH-H ₂ O (1 : 1)	50	60	80
15	PSA	5 mol %	EtOH-H ₂ O (1 : 1)	70	45	94
16	Cu(OTf) ₂	5 mol %	EtOH-H ₂ O (1 : 1)	60	120	64
17	<i>p</i> -TsOH	5 mol %	EtOH-H ₂ O (1 : 1)	60	90	75
18	SA	5 mol %	EtOH-H ₂ O (1 : 1)	60	90	66

^aReaction conditions : 2-aminobenzamide **1a** (1 mmol) and benzaldehyde **2a** (1 mmol), solvent 5 mL. ^bIsolated yield.

mixture. The results indicated that the best conversion was observed when the reaction was performed in EtOH-H₂O (1 : 1) (Table 1, entry 8). Based on these results, EtOH-H₂O (1 : 1) was then selected as reaction medium for further investigations.

Next, we have evaluated the influence of different amounts of catalyst using 0, 5, 2, 3, 7 mol % of PSA on the model cyclocondensation reaction of 2-amino-benzamide (1 mmol) and benzaldehyde (1 mmol) in EtOH-H₂O (1 : 1) at 60 °C (Table 1, entries 8–12). It was observed that 5 mol % of PSA was the best of amount of the catalyst at 60 °C (Table 1, entry 8). Using lower amounts of catalyst resulted in lower yields, while higher amounts of catalyst did not affect the reaction times and yields (Table 1, entries 8–12). Also, this reaction was checked under different temperatures including 60 and RT, 50 and 70 °C (Table 1, entry 8 and entries 13–15). The greatest yield in the shortest reaction time was ob-

tained in EtOH-H₂O (1 : 1) at 60 °C in the presence of 5 mol % of PSA.

To show that PSA is an efficient catalyst, we accomplished the model reaction in the presence of catalysts, such as copper(II) triflate (Cu(OTf)₂), *p*-toluene sulfonic acid (*p*-TsOH), and sulfamic acid (SA) (Table 1, entries 16–18). Tested catalysts gave lower yields compared with PSA (Table 1, entry 8). Thus, EtOH-H₂O (1 : 1) at 60 °C and 5 mol % of PSA were chosen as the optimum system to extend the protocol.

To test the generality of this reaction, a series of aromatic aldehydes with both electron-donating and electron-withdrawing substituents were reacted with 2-amino-benzamide under the optimized reaction conditions, and the corresponding 2,3-dihydro-2-phenylquinazolin-4(1*H*)-ones (**3a–l**) were obtained in short reaction times. The results are summarized in Table 2. From these experiments, it is clearly demonstrated that the synthesis of 2,3-

Table 2. Synthesis of various 2,3-dihydro-2-phenylquinazolin-4(1*H*)-ones in the presence of PSA (5 mol %)^a

Entry	Aldehyde	Product	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^b	M.p (°C)	
					Found	Reported
1		45	94	221–223	218–219 [8]	
2		60	88	226–228	225–226 [15]	
3		45	95	265–267	266–267 [8]	
4		45	92	223–225	223–225 [15]	
5		60	87	228–230	228–229 [8]	

Table-2 (contd.)

6		45	92	202–204	205–206 [8]	
7		60	89	232–234	233–234 [8]	
8		60	88	184–186	184–186 [15]	
9		60	92	277–279	278–280 [8]	
10		50	91	216–218	216–217 [8]	
11		45	90	202–204	199–200 [8]	
12		50	92	190–192	190–191 [13]	

^aReaction conditions : 2-aminobenzamide (1 mmol) and benzaldehyde (1 mmol) at 60 °C. ^bIsolated yield.

dihydroquinazolin-4(1*H*)-ones using PSA as catalyst in EtOH-H₂O (1 : 1) at 60 °C is indeed an effective method and is undoubtedly superior to other procedures with respect to reaction time, availability of catalyst, work-up procedure and yields.

The reusability of the catalyst is one of the most important green aspects by avoiding toxic catalyst³¹. The recycling performance of the PSA was investigated using a model reaction between 2-aminobenzamide and benzaldehyde in the presence of 5 mol% of the catalyst in EtOH-H₂O (1 : 1) at 60 °C. After the separation of product, the

catalyst was washed with diethyl ether and vacuumed to remove diethyl ether and the resulting catalyst was re-used directly for the next run. As shown in Fig. 1, the recycled catalyst was used for further runs and its activity did not show any significant decrease even after four runs, the yields ranged from 94% to 88% (94%, 92%, 90% and 88%).

A tentative mechanism for the formation of 2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1*H*)-ones was proposed (Scheme 2). The addition of nucleophiles to the aldehydes is promoted by protonation of the carbonyl group with the aid of PSA

Fig. 1. Recycling of catalyst PSA for the synthesis of 2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1*H*)-one.

Scheme 2. Proposed mechanism for the formation of 2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1*H*)-ones.

and enhancing the electrophilicity of this moiety³². The proton from PSA is donated to the oxygen atom of the

aldehyde. Therefore, it is proposed that, at first, the reaction starts through nucleophilic attack of the amino group in 2-amino benzamide at the activated carbonyl group in arylaldehyde by PSA. It seems that the reaction proceeds through intermediate **4**, such that after dehydration, the imine intermediate **5** is produced. Then, the intermediate **5** undergo protonation and heterocyclization to furnish the corresponding 2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1*H*)-ones.

Experimental

Chemicals and apparatus :

Chemicals were purchased from Merck, Fluka and Aldrich Chemical Companies. All yields refer to isolated products unless otherwise stated. ¹H NMR (500 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (125 MHz) spectra were obtained using Bruker DRX-500 Avance at ambient temperature, using TMS as internal standard. FT-IR spectra were obtained as KBr discs on Shimadzu spectrometer. Mass spectra were determined on a Varion-Saturn 2000 GC/MS instrument. Elemental analyses were measured by means of Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN elemental analyzer flowchart.

Preparation of phospho sulfonic acid :

Phospho sulfonic acid (PSA) was easily prepared according to the previously reported method²¹ (Scheme 3). A 50 mL suction flask was equipped with a constant pressure dropping funnel. The gas outlet was connected to a vacuum system through an alkali solution trap. Diammonium hydrogen phosphate (2 g, 15 mmol) was charged into the flask and chlorosulfonic acid (5.24 g, *ca.* 3 mL, 45 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (10 mL) was added dropwise over a period of 30 min at room temperature. After completion of the addition, the mixture was shaken for 2 h, while the residual HCl was eliminated by suction. Then the mixture was washed with excess dried CH₂Cl₂. Finally, a solid white powder (4.2 g) was obtained.

Scheme 3. Preparation of phospho sulfonic acid (PSA).

General procedure for the synthesis of 2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-ones :

To a solution of 2-aminobenzamide (1 mmol) and aldehyde (1 mmol) in EtOH-H₂O (1 : 1) (5 mL), PSA (5 mol %) was added. The mixture was stirred at 60 °C for an appropriate time. After completion of the reaction, as indicated by TLC (ethyl acetate : *n*-hexane 1 : 1), hot ethanol (5 mL) was added to the residue which was then filtered. The resulting solution was condensed under reduced pressure. Finally the crude product was purified by recrystallization from EtOH to afford the corresponding 2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-ones in 87–95% yield.

*Spectroscopic data for synthesised compounds (3a-l) :**2,3-Dihydro-2-phenylquinazolin-4(1H)-one (3a) :*

White solid; IR (KBr) : 3298, 3163, 3049, 1655, 1607, 1500, 1472 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 5.60 (1H, s, CH), 6.77 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, Ar-H), 6.88 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.18 (1H, br s, NH), 7.26 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.35–7.44 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.70 (2H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.80 (1H, d, *J* 7.7 Hz, Ar-H), 8.42 (1H, br s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 68.0, 112.9, 116.0, 117.5, 127.3, 128.2, 129.4, 129.7, 133.3, 142.4, 148.8, 167.4 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 225 (M+H)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₂N₂O (%) : C, 75.00; H, 5.36; N, 12.50. Found : C, 74.86; H, 5.34; N, 12.47.

2-(2-Chlorophenyl)-2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-one (3b) :

White solid; IR (KBr) : 3294, 3171, 3064, 1664, 1614, 1504, 1474 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 5.74 (1H, s, CH), 6.73 (1H, t, *J* 8.3 Hz, Ar-H), 6.82 (1H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.12 (1H, br s, NH), 7.29–7.38 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.43 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.77 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, Ar-H), 8.45 (1H, br s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 67.4, 113.4, 116.2, 117.3, 127.2, 128.2, 129.4, 129.9, 133.4, 142.8, 148.5, 166.4 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 259 (M+H)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₁ClN₂O (%) : C, 65.00; H, 4.26; N, 10.83. Found : C, 64.89; H, 4.20; N, 10.84.

2-(3-Fluorophenyl)-2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-one (3c) :

White solid; IR (KBr) : 3306, 3167, 3052, 1664, 1610, 1511, 1472 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 5.75 (1H, s, CH), 6.75 (1H, t, *J* 8.1 Hz, Ar-H), 6.90

(1H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.14 (1H, br s, NH), 7.30–7.45 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.51 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.72 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, Ar-H), 8.40 (1H, br s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 67.4, 113.0, 116.4, 117.4, 127.0, 128.3, 129.4, 129.4, 133.1, 142.3, 148.3, 166.6 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 243 (M+H)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₁FN₂O (%) : C, 69.42; H, 4.55; N, 11.57. Found : C, 69.37; H, 4.49; N, 11.56.

2-(3-Bromophenyl)-2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-one (3d) :

White solid; IR (KBr) : 3298, 3177, 3065, 1652, 1615, 1510, 1470 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 5.66 (1H, s, CH), 6.70–6.82 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.15 (1H, s, NH), 7.33 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.44 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.60–7.68 (3H, m, Ar-H), 8.40 (1H, s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 68.2, 113.2, 116.4, 117.7, 127.5, 128.6, 129.0, 129.4, 133.8, 142.8, 147.8, 168.5 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 303.5 (M+H)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₁BrN₂O (%) : C, 55.46; H, 3.63; N, 9.24. Found : C, 55.39; H, 3.58; N, 9.17.

2-(4-N,N-Dimethylaminophenyl)-2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-one (3e) :

White solid; IR (KBr) : 3300, 3162, 3055, 1655, 1605, 1514, 1487 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 2.93 (6H, s, N(CH₃)₂), 5.55 (1H, s, CH), 6.75 (1H, t, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 6.88 (1H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.14 (1H, br s, NH), 7.36–7.49 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.64 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.77 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, Ar-H), 8.40 (1H, br s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 42.5, 67.9, 114.3, 116.7, 117.4, 127.32, 128.0, 129.2, 129.6, 133.1, 142.3, 148.4, 166.7 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 268 (M+H)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₇N₃O (%) : C, 71.91; H, 6.37; N, 15.73. Found : C, 71.88; H, 6.34; N, 15.72.

2-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-one (3f) :

White solid; IR (KBr) : 3288, 3177, 3066, 1665, 1614, 1502, 1471 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 5.69 (1H, s, CH), 6.77 (1H, t, *J* 8.3 Hz, Ar-H), 6.85 (1H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.05 (1H, br s, NH), 7.25–7.37 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.47 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.73 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, Ar-H), 8.46 (1H, br s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 68.3, 112.5, 116.3, 117.5, 127.8, 128.6, 129.7, 130.3, 133.7, 143.3, 148.8, 166.8 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 259 (M+H)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for

$C_{14}H_{11}ClN_2O$ (%): C, 65.00; H, 4.26; N, 10.83. Found : C, 64.90; H, 4.21; N, 10.81.

2-(4-Methylphenyl)-2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-one (**3g**) :

White solid; IR (KBr) : 3309, 3178, 3059, 1662, 1615, 1512, 1485 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.23 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.70 (1H, s, CH), 6.79 (1H, t, *J* 8.1 Hz, Ar-H), 7.00 (1H, d, *J* 6.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.16 (1H, br s, NH), 7.37–7.47 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.56 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.82 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, Ar-H), 8.46 (1H, br s, NH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 21.4, 68.5, 113.4, 116.3, 117.8, 127.6, 128.4, 129.5, 130.1, 133.7, 142.9, 147.9, 166.9 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 239 (M+H)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{14}N_2O$ (%) : C, 75.63; H, 5.88; N, 11.76. Found : C, 75.55; H, 5.80; N, 11.71.

2-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-one (**3h**) :

White solid; IR (KBr) : 3303, 3167, 3066, 1661, 1619, 1500, 1474 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 3.63 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.71 (1H, s, CH), 6.77–6.85 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.14 (1H, s, NH), 7.30 (1H, d, *J* 7.9 Hz, Ar-H), 7.56 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.70–7.79 (3H, m, Ar-H), 8.46 (1H, s, NH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 55.0, 67.3, 112.7, 116.7, 117.7, 127.6, 128.6, 129.5, 130.3, 133.7, 142.9, 147.8, 167.4 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 255 (M+H)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{14}N_2O_2$ (%) : C, 70.87; H, 5.51; N, 11.02. Found : C, 70.72; H, 5.42; N, 11.00.

2-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)-2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-one (**3i**) :

White solid; IR (KBr) : 3303, 3170, 3044, 1660, 1617, 1508, 1481 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 5.74 (1H, s, CH), 6.74–6.86 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.21 (1H, s, NH), 7.37 (1H, d, *J* 7.9 Hz, Ar-H), 7.53 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.68–7.78 (3H, m, Ar-H), 8.49 (1H, s, NH), 9.88 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 68.3, 112.4, 116.5, 117.2, 127.1, 128.1, 129.3, 129.7, 133.2, 143.3, 148.5, 167.4 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 241 (M+H)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{12}N_2O_2$ (%) : C, 70.00; H, 5.00; N, 11.67. Found : C, 69.94; H, 4.98; N, 11.68.

2-(3-Nitrophenyl)-2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-one (**3j**) :

White solid; IR (KBr) : 3300, 3170, 3066, 1657, 1617,

1507, 1485 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 5.70 (1H, s, CH), 6.77 (1H, t, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 6.93 (1H, d, *J* 6.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.15 (1H, br s, NH), 7.27–7.40 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.56 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.61–7.65 (1H, m, Ar-H), 8.42 (1H, br s, NH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 67.4, 112.6, 116.5, 117.2, 127.2, 128.4, 129.0, 129.5, 133.4, 143.2, 148.8, 166.8 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 270 (M+H)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{11}N_3O_3$ (%) : C, 62.45; H, 4.09; N, 15.61. Found : C, 62.38; H, 4.04; N, 15.62.

2-(4-Fluorophenyl)-2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-one (**3k**) :

White solid; IR (KBr) : 3285, 3155, 3056, 1649, 1600, 1514, 1468 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 5.77 (1H, s, CH), 6.72 (1H, t, *J* 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 6.96 (1H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.10 (1H, br s, NH), 7.22–7.35 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.52 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.62–7.70 (1H, m, Ar-H), 8.42 (1H, br s, NH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 67.4, 113.2, 116.4, 117.8, 127.6, 128.4, 129.0, 129.6, 133.4, 143.3, 148.5, 167.6 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 243 (M+H)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{11}FN_2O$ (%) : C, 69.42; H, 4.55; N, 11.57. Found : C, 69.35; H, 4.51; N, 11.53.

2-(3-Hydroxyphenyl)-2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-one (**3l**) :

White solid; IR (KBr) : 3290, 3167, 3061, 1655, 1610, 1510, 1475 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 5.72 (1H, s, CH), 6.77 (1H, t, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 6.95 (1H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.03 (1H, br s, NH), 7.20–7.35 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.57 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.69–7.74 (1H, m, Ar-H), 8.47 (1H, br s, NH), 9.93 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 67.9, 112.5, 116.5, 117.5, 127.8, 128.6, 129.5, 129.9, 133.8, 142.7, 147.8, 167.5 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 241 (M+H)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{12}N_2O_2$ (%) : C, 70.00; H, 5.00; N, 11.67. Found : C, 69.92; H, 4.94; N, 11.64.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we have found an efficient and practical procedure for the preparation of 2,3-dihydroquinazolin-4(1H)-ones catalyzed by phosphosulfonic acid (PSA) at

60 °C in EtOH-H₂O (1 : 1) medium. The current method has the advantages of high yields, simple procedure, easy work-up, high catalytic activity and recyclability and re-usability of the catalyst.

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